

Chemical Components of *Adina cordifolia* Leaves

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Adina cordifolia (Family: Rubiaceae) is found scattered in deciduous forests throughout the greater part of India, ascending to an altitude of 900 m in the sub-Himalayan tract. It is also common in the forests of South India. Its heartwood was found to contain a yellow pigment adinin, adifoline, cordifoline and a number of other compounds¹⁻³. The bark is acrid and bitter, and is used in biliousness¹. It has also been chemically investigated⁴. The roots are used as an astringent in dysentery¹. The leaves are used as fodder¹. Since there is no report on the chemical constituents of leaves, the present investigation was taken up. Two compounds A and B were isolated and characterised from the acetone and alcohol extracts respectively.

The air dried leaves (700 g) collected from Forest Research Institute campus were extracted with petroleum ether, acetone and alcohol separately. Column chromatography of the acetone extract and n-butanol soluble portion of the alcohol extract gave compounds A and B respectively.

Compound A (1.75 g) was obtained on elution with C₆H₆-MeOH (95:5) and crystallised from CHCl₃-MeOH as white needles, m.p. 291-92°; acetate m.p. 285-86°, [α]_D+57.5° (CHCl₃); methyl ester acetate, m.p. 238-40° and gave positive L. B. test (pink→blue). It was characterised as ursolic acid⁵ by nmr spectra and direct comparison with authentic sample (m.m.p., co-tlc and superimposable ir spectra).

Compound B was eluted with CHCl₃-MeOH (4:1) and crystallised from methanol as yellow crystals (650 mg), m.p. 236-38°, [α]_D-55° (c, 0.465 in MeOH); λ_{\max} (MeOH) (log ϵ) 256.3 (4.20), 359.8 (4.0)4; + (AlCl₃) 273.2, 417.3; (+ AlCl₃+HCl)

267.9, 398.6; (+NaOAc) 273.5, 322.2, 386.2; (+NaOAc+H₃BO₃) 261.5, 379.5; (+NaOH) 272.1 (4.34), 338.8 (4.05), 404.5 (4.24) nm; ν_{\max} (KBr) 3350br and 1655 cm⁻¹; acetate, m.p. 120-21°. It yielded quercetin and galactose on hydrolysis and furnished tetra-O-methylquercetin on methylation followed by hydrolysis. These results and the comparison of its ¹³C-nmr and other spectral data with those reported for quercetin 3-O-galactoside⁶ characterised the compound as quercetin 3-O-galactoside.

This is the first report of their occurrence in the leaves.

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